

Influence of Gender and School Location on Performance in Agricultural Science among Secondary School Students in Kaduna North, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to establish the influence of gender and school location on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Agricultural Science students, using secondary data obtained from National Examination Council (NECO) results of 2018 to 2022. Survey design was used in a school population of 101, in the eight Local Governments of the zone, while multi-stage purposive sampling was used to select six schools from three school types in rural and urban locations. Two Senior Secondary schools in each of the school types were randomly selected. Data were subjected to descriptive statistics of means and percent, while independent t-test ($p \leq 0.05$) was used to test null hypotheses. Results revealed a fairly consistent increase in enrolment over the period, where male (56.74%) and urban (55.86%) students dominated enrolment. Results also showed variation in general results and quality of performance, which favoured the male (46.80%) and urban (43.69%) students compared to female (31.89%) and rural (35.15%) counterparts. However, there were no significant difference in enrolment and performance of gender and school location. The study therefore established that gender and school location does not have strong influence on students' performance, using National Examination Council of Nigeria results. Hence recommended that, the relatively low female enrolment, and poor performance of females and rural students are *sine qua non* to state government and other educational stakeholders for improved and sustainable students' performance, achievable through engagement of adequate and experienced teachers, motivation of staff and students, as well as retraining of teachers.

Keywords: Gender, location, enrolment, Performance, learning and Agricultural Science

Introduction

Agricultural Science is seen as one of the main vocational subjects taught in all Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria based on the National Policy on Education (Newton and Hamisu, 2023). This is because of its roles towards making its beneficiaries self-reliance via provision of gainful employment chances, supply of staple foods to the ever-increasing population and generating raw materials to agro-based industries. Agriculture based on Onwunali, Muhammad and Balogun (2022) assertion is an integral factor in the development of any developing economy. This makes its teaching imperative at all level of education in the country with Senior Secondary Schools being a prominent foundation and link for higher education. Meanwhile Agricultural Science is a field of learning that emphasized understanding and utilization of scarce environmental resources towards food production to meet the need of increasing population of Nigeria. The teaching of this subject did not evolve without its own peculiarity. Teaching Agricultural Science usually goes along establishment of the three domains of learning to bring about better understanding and performance to its beneficiaries in the school and thereafter.

Academic achievement is the outcome of education, the extent which learner, teacher or institution has achieved their set goals. This is commonly measured by continuous assessment and examination (Oriakhi and Ujoro, 2015). Even though assessment still remains the only way to measure performance, there has not been generally agreed best ways of carrying it out. There are two divides of the coin of performance which is good and poor performance. Poor performance is when a learner achievement is below his actual ability and otherwise good performance is when the learner achievement is equal to or above his actual ability. Poor or good performance could happen as a result of several factors among which are environment, gender,

social among others (Alordiah, Akpadaka and Oviogbodun, 2015). Onwunali *et al.* (2022) reported that reading habit and achievement influenced each other while both are affected by environment. According to the authors, a convenient and conducive learning environment creates favourable reading atmosphere hence, improved academic achievement. Contrarily, poor and unconducive environment influence performance negatively. According to Iroko, Adesin and Asanre, (2024), many social divide factors are influencing learners' performance at secondary schools level. These factors include access to resources, quality of resources, quality of teachers, culture and language differences, gender disparity and environment to mention but few.

Location means position of the school within the chosen area of study. School location may be rural or urban in nature. Newton and Hamisu (2023) defined rural setting as settlement away from cities which may be lacking major social infrastructures such as health facilities, pipe borne water, electricity, good road network *inter alia*, while urban have all the required amenities. School locations are one of the factors affecting achievement level of students. It was established that rural dwellers are slow-witted hillbillies with little or no education and not current of happenings (Akinwumi, 2017). Alordiah *et al.* (2015) asserted that students attending rural schools face challenges of high poverty than those in urban schools. But they still maintained that rural schools have advantage of smaller classes which assist in flexibility of teaching/learning. In Agricultural Science the rural schools are at advantage for the fact that land is abundant for practical.

In the words of Oriakhi and Ujoro (2015), gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity. It may mean sex (biological) as in male and female and in social structure (it may be gender roles) or gender identity. Gender is a socially construed trait of male and female in a given community different from sex. Gender differences in academic performance have generated serious interest in educational research over the years (Iroko *et al.*, 2024). Gender issues are currently assuming prominence in research globally, and have generated high consideration among academia and policy makers. This is unconnected with disparities in the allocation of cognitive roles in world of work. Meanwhile, gender inequality in enrolment is also influencing performance since boys are dominating in Agricultural Science. This has been associated with female poor performance in the subject (Onwunali *et al.*, 2022).

Agricultural Science as a vocational subject is taught with emphasis on hands on practical (Onwunali, 2024), consequently in teaching the subject cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of learning are paramount. The psychomotor domain requires the use of farm activities of both livestock and crops of various types, which is not common in most urban schools due to lack of farm (Omodara, Onwunali and Joshua, 2024), and where farms are available in rural schools are not effectively used based on policy establishing Agricultural Science as vocational subject. At times students from urban areas perceived Agricultural Science as dirty job while the female students tend to shy away from the subject due to lack of interest, stereotype attitude and the claim that Agricultural Science practical is tedious. Onwunali *et al.* (2022) stated that Nigerian youths mainly choose Agricultural Science on a second thought when they fail in Medicine and Pharmacy, and associated it to students' lack of interest, attitude and poor performance in the course. As if that is not enough, speculations are bound that most students residing in urban environment hardly have background experience in farming like their rural counterparts hence the ugly perception in Agricultural Science.

Furthermore, much have been published on students' performance using West African Examination Council (WAEC) examination results with relatively meagre or no information on National Examination Council (NECO), which is also an acceptable and accredited 'O' Level examination body. The West African Examination Council and NECO are the two standard 'O' level examination councils in Nigeria, that uses professional agricultural educators to evaluate students. Such is achieved through questions that covers the three domains of learning based on the 3-year curriculum of the Senior Secondary Schools, and have same grading system (A1-F9) (Udofia and Udoh, 2017). However, speculations are bound on superiority of WAEC over NECO possibly because WAEC is a sub-regional examination, and the perception that academic achievement is sure at relatively low cost with NECO (Agwu, Orjiakor, Odii, Onalu, Nzeadibe and Okoye, 2020). Furthermore, laxity in monitoring and supervision of students in Senior Secondary Schools metamorphosed into ill practices such as 'Miracle Centres' or 'Special Centres', as a means of coping with academic pressures for good grades (Onyedinefu, 2019; Agwu *et al.*, 2020; Abioye, 2021; Obeza, 2023). The rot is further exacerbated with parental factors, mostly public office holders and educators, probably due to the weak enforcement of the Examination Malpractice Act of 1999 which sets out terms of imprisonment and fines (Agwu *et al.*, 2020).

Based on the foregoing therefore, the main objective of the study is to establish the influence of gender and school location on students' performance, using NECO results. This is because such information with NECO results are relatively meagre compared to West African Examination Council Examination.

Objectives of the Study

The activities that established gender and location effect on student achievement included to;

1. Determine gender and school location enrolment of students in the study area,
2. Evaluate the relative performance of male and female students in Kaduna North Senatorial District,
3. Assess performance of students at rural and urban schools in the study area.

The study was guided by the following questions;

1. What is the distribution of students by gender (male and female) and school location (rural and urban) in Kaduna North Senatorial District?
2. What is the relative academic performance of male and female students in Kaduna North Senatorial District?
3. What differences exist between academic performance of students attending rural and urban schools in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ were tested to justify the interactions between gender, school location, enrolment and performance;

1. **H₀₁**; There is no significant difference between the enrolment of male and female students in the rural and urban environment in Agricultural Science in the study area.
2. **H₀₂**; There is no significant difference between the performance of male and female Agricultural Science students in the study area.
3. **H₀₃**; There is no significant difference between the performance of rural and urban Agricultural Science students in the study area.

Methodology

The study covered Northern Senatorial District of Kaduna State which comprised of eight Local Government Areas of Ikara, Kubau, Kudan, Lere, Makarfi, Sabon-Gari, Soba and Zaria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study area comprised of 101 registered public Senior Secondary Schools in Kaduna. (KSASCR, 2020). A multi stage purposive sampling was adopted in selecting the six Secondary Schools based on location (3 rural schools and 3 urban schools). The three school types selected were two single male school, two single female school and mixed (co-education) school from both environmental settings.

The study was based on the secondary data obtained from National Examination Council (NECO) results for five years spanning through 2018 to 2022 for Agricultural Science. A total of 2,254 students were involved in the study, representing number of students that registered for the subject within the five years. Of the total of 2,254 students, 995 were from urban while 1,259 were rural students, but in gender, male students recorded 1279 as against the female (975) students. The data were confidentially collected from the Zonal Education Office in the zone, using grading system A₁, B₂, B₃, C₄, C₅, C₆, D₇, E₈ and F₉ (Onwunali, Muhammad and Omodara, 2024), and was complimented with results from selected schools. Such grading results were summative and formative, where A₁ represents Distinction, B₂ represents Very good, B₃ represents Good, C₄ to C₆ represents Credit, D₇ - E₈ represents Pass, and F₉ represents Fail. The grades A₁ to C₆ were regarded as quality performance in this study, considering that C₆ is the minimum grade required for further studies in post secondary education. Data were subjected to descriptive analysis of means, frequency and percent while independent t-test ($p \leq 0.05$) was used to test significance of the null hypotheses. All analysis were performed using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.

Presentation of Results

Question 1: What is the distribution of students by gender (male and female) and school location (rural and urban) in Kaduna North Senatorial District?.

Results (Table 1) showed a general enrolment of 56.74% for male students and 43.26% for female, where 55.86% and 44.14% of the students were located in urban and rural areas, respectively. Furthermore, results revealed a fairly consistent increase in enrolment from 2018 to 2022 for male and urban students and inconsistent in female and rural students which recorded 10.34% and 9.63% in 2022. Results also showed high mean value for male (255.80) and urban (251.40) students' enrolment, compare to the female and rural counterparts. Specifically, relative enrolment of male students was 8.39% in 2018 and 13.30% in 2022 while the female enrolment was 6.74% and 10.83% in 2018 and 2021, respectively. In location, urban

enrolment was 8.92% and 14.19% in 2018 and 2022, respectively, while rural relatively recorded 6.21% in 2018 and 19.63% in 2022.

Results clearly indicated that, despite the mean variations in enrolment, the independent t-test value of 2.067 ($p > 0.05$) for gender and 1.732 ($p > 0.05$) for location were not statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$) using Senior Secondary Schools NECO results. Therefore, the null hypotheses which stated that there is no significant difference between the enrolment of male and female students in rural and urban environment in Agricultural Science were accepted.

Table 1: Sex and school location enrolment of Senior Secondary Agricultural Science in the North Senatorial District of Kaduna State.

Year	Sex		Location	
	Male	Female	Rural	Urban
2018	189(8.39)	152(6.74)	140(6.21)	201(8.92)
2019	212(9.41)	166(7.36)	167(7.19)	214(9.49)
2020	288(12.78)	180(7.99)	237(10.51)	231(9.45)
2021	290(12.86)	244(10.83)	237(10.51)	297(9.45)
2022	300(13.30)	233(10.34)	216(9.63)	314(14.19)
Total	1279(56.74)	975(43.26)	997(44.14)	1257(55.86)
Mean	255.80±22.95	195.00±18.38	199.40±19.59	251.40±22.75
Sig. ($p \leq 0.05$)	t-value = 2.067, ($p > 0.05$) NS		t-value = -1.732, ($p > 0.05$) NS	

Source: Field survey, 2023 Numbers in bracket are percent of the corresponding numbers of sex and location enrolments per year, \pm = standard error of difference of mean, NS = not significant, null hypothesis was accepted, using t test independent value.

Question 2: What is the relative academic performance of male and female students in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Results in Table 2 showed that, of the 2254 students that sat for examination within the period, 94.48% generally passed at grades A1 to E8 for both gender. However, the male students had relatively high mean (54.61%) compared to 38.87% of the females. Similarly, on quality of performance (A1-C6), 78.70% had good grades, corresponding to 'A' grade (Excellent), which by relative performance favoured the males (46.81%) more than the females (31.89%). Furthermore, mean performance of the male students was also relatively high (141.88) compared to the females (107.55). However, despite high enrolment of the males, relative failure rate of the female students were high (3.25%) compared to 2.27% of the males students.

The independent t-test value of 0.648 ($p > 0.05$) statistically showed that, there is no significant difference on the performance of male and female students. Hence the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the performance of male and female students in Agricultural Science was accepted. The relatively high mean may probably be due to high enrolment of males and inability of girls to participate in farm practical.

Table 2: Relative performance of male and female Senior Secondary student in Agricultural Science in North Kaduna Senatorial District.

Grade	Male			Female		
	F	%	QP	F	%	QP
A1	19	0.85		3	0.13	
B2	53	2.36		14	0.62	
B3	85	3.79		46	2.05	
C4	229	10.20		122	5.43	
C5	353	15.72		239	10.65	
C6	312	13.89	46.81	292	13.01	31.89
D7	120	5.35		116	5.17	
E8	55	2.45 (54.61)		63	2.81(38.87)	
F9	51	2.27		73	3.25	
Total	1277	56.88		968	43.12	
Mean	141.88±41.43			107.55±32.96		
Sig. ($p \leq 0.05$)	t-value = 0.648, ($p > 0.05$) NS					

Source: Field survey, 2023, *Number that sat for examination between 2018 to 2022 = 2254, F = frequency of male and female students per grade, % = relative percentage performance of students per grade, QP = quality of performance of students, NS = not significant, null hypothesis was accepted, using t test independent value*

Question 3: What differences exist between academic performance of students attending rural and urban schools in Kaduna North Senatorial District?

Results in Table 3 revealed 94.61% at A1 to E8 pass grades in both locations, with relatively high performance in the urban environment (52.55%) than the 42.06% of the rural. The mean performance values of 139.55 and 109.88 for urban and rural areas, respectively were also evident. Results also showed 78.84% quality performance, where urban students had high scores (43.69%) than the rural (35.15%), probably due to high enrolment, availability and quality teachers, and facilities that are relatively inadequate in the rural setting. Results also recorded high failure in the urban (3.39%) compared to rural (2.00%), possibly due to high enrolment thereof. Nevertheless variation in means, using independent t-test value of 0.564 ($P 0.581 > 0.05$), did not reveal significant difference between the performance of urban and rural students. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the performance of urban and rural students in Agricultural Science was accepted. The result implied that, performance of students in NECO Agricultural Science between rural and urban areas are relative, possibly due to the examination organization which creates opportunity for malpractice. The high performance in general results and quality may probably be associated with the speculation of poor examination organization.

Table 3: Relative performance of Agricultural Science students in rural and urban Senior Secondary Schools in North Senatorial District of Kaduna State

Grade	Rural			Urban		
	F	%	QP	F	%	QP
A1	7	0.31		15	0.67	
B2	17	0.76		50	2.23	
B3	21	0.94		110	4.90	
C4	141	6.28		210	9.35	
C5	283	12.61		309	13.76	
C6	320	14.25	35.15	287	12.78	43.69
D7	112	4.99		124	5.52	
E8	43	1.92(42.06)		75	3.34(52.55)	
F9	45	2.00		76	3.39	
Total	989	44.05		1256	55.95	
Mean	109.88±39.24			139.55±35.01		
Sig. ($p \leq 0.05$)	t-value = -0.564, ($p 0.581 > 0.05$) NS					

Source: Field survey, 2023, *Number that sat for examination between 2018 to 2022 = 2254, F = Number of students per grade, % = relative percentage performance of students per grade, QP = quality of performance of students, NS = not significant, null hypothesis was accepted, using t test independent value*

Discussion of Findings

Results of research question 1 showed that, despite the high enrolment of male and urban students, there was no significant statistical difference between gender and location enrolment in Kaduna North, using NECO Senior Secondary results in public schools. The results also revealed fairly and consistent increase in enrolment of male and urban student, contrary to the fluctuating pattern in female and rural enrolment. Earlier, Onwunali *et al.* (2024) reported fluctuating enrolment of students in Agricultural science which favoured the males student as observed in the study, although there were no significant difference. The female students tend to shy away due to the practical activities in the crop and animal farm practical which they perceived as tedious and requires much energy (Olukayode and Ayoola, 2015; Muhammad *et al.*, 2022). Although many studies have reported a strong correlation between the performance of students in WAEC and NECO examinations (Ogini *et al.*, 2024), inconsistency in the enrolment of students in WAEC (Nwanosike, 2013) may have been probably due to drift of student to NECO due to perceived idea for success through examination malpractice, resulting in the consistent increase in enrolment for NECO. Similarly, Muhammad *et al.* (2022) reported high enrolment of students in urban than rural environment due to drift as a result of rural urban migration and inadequate facilities associated with the rural location.

Question 2 revealed high but no significant performance that favoured the male students, which is in conformity with Nzewi (2010) and Dorgu (2015), who reported that male students performed better in practical oriented vocational and science

subjects. However, the insignificant results implied that male and female performance was at par, probably due to the females' lack of interest in practical aspect of the subject. The high-quality performance of students may have probably confirmed the earlier speculation of compromise among supervisors on examination matter. Such general and quality performance is very difficult in WAEC results (Onwunali, *et al.*, 2022). Otherwise, Alordiah, *et al.*, (2015) also concluded that, given equal opportunity there is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students.

On the contrary, Anyaegbu *et al.* (2016) and Newton and Hamisu, (2023) agreed that there is significant difference between academic performance of boys and girls in Agricultural Science. Similarly, Nnenna and Adukwu (2018) in Biology established a significant difference in male and female in favour of male students in Agbani Education Zone of Enugu State. Obviously, in many rural communities, girls are subjected to several barriers such as early marriage, cultural and religious barriers like *Kulle* (Onwunali, *et al.*, 2022) as well as domestic responsibilities that may probably limit their educational opportunities, performance and transition to higher institutions of learning (UNESCO, 2011; Felix, 2018).

Results in question 3 showed that, location was not a strong factor in students' academic achievement. Earlier, Yusuf and Adigun (2010) reported that school location had no significant influence on students' academic achievement. Similar to Jack and Sam (2020) who revealed that, there is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of rural and urban students in Biology. On the contrary, Onwunali, *et al.*, (2022) concluded that location had significant influence on student performance in Agricultural Science in Zaria and Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, using WAEC results.

Schools in urban areas have better access to educational facilities, teaching materials and teachers than schools in rural settings who struggle with inadequate infrastructure like classrooms and teaching materials like textbooks, and even inadequate qualified subject teachers which are key components to improved students' academic performance (Abioye, 2021; Obeza, 2023). Hence subjected to poor academic output due to improper guidance of poor rural teachers that prefer farming and small businesses instead of the primary assignment (Onwunali *et al.*, 2022). However, evidence of better rural performance have been reported (Mberepe, 2013).

In Nigeria, when qualified teachers are posted to these rural locations, they manoeuvre their way back to urban areas or at most abandon their duty post with sporadic report to work due poor incentive from the government and absence of basic amenities such as electricity and accessible roads in most rural areas (Obeza, 2023). Consequently, consolidating the ill practice of establishing miracle centres in rural schools, as examination officers tend to focus their supervision in the urban schools, giving corrupt individuals the opportunity to manipulate examination in the rural areas.

Conclusion

Results from the study evidently showed that, there were no statistically significant differences between relative enrolment and performance of male and female in rural and urban environments in Agricultural Science. Therefore, study concluded that, using the NECO results of 2018 to 2022, gender and school location had no significant influence on the enrolment and achievement of Agricultural Science students in Senior Secondary Schools in Kaduna North Senatorial District of Kaduna State.

Recommendations

From the findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Kaduna State government should implement the National Policy on Education by recognizing Agricultural Science as a basic vocational subject that should be compulsory for all candidates in primary and Junior Secondary Schools to encourage the female students enrolment in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. The relatively poor performance of female students due to their perceived tedious nature of Agricultural Science should be encouraged through motivation (awards) and effective counselling units in schools, by educational stakeholders such as school management, parent teachers association, school Alumni, school community, Local and State Government.
3. The relatively poor performance of the rural students should be encouraged through provision of trained and qualified teachers, as well as facilities for teaching by government at all levels particularly the local and state governments.

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